

P! GALERIE
"SELECTION OF MASTERPIECES"
CHARLOTTE PERRIAND
GERRIT RIETVELD
LE CORBUSIER
LINA BO BARDI
MARCEL BREUER
PIERRE JEANNERET
TOM STRALA

VILLA E-1027

ROQUEBRUNE-CAP-MARTIN

GRAY WAS A NON-CONFORMIST AND DID NOT CARE MUCH ABOUT SOCIETY'S TRADITIONS. RATHER, SHE PREFERRED TO SPEND HER TIME IN PARISIAN BARS DRESSED UP AS A MAN WITH HER GIRLFRIEND, ABSORBING THE GREAT SPIRIT OF THE 1920S.

VILLA E-1027, PAINTED WOOD, LEATHER
ROQUEBRUNE-CAP-MARTIN
30.25 X 23.50 X 23.50 IN (77 X 60 X 60 CM)

THE ARMCHAIR ORIGINATES FROM EILEEN GRAY'S PERSONAL COLLECTION AT VILLA E-1027 IN ROQUEBRUNE AND FROM HER FLAT IN THE RUE BONAPARTE IN PARIS. THE PIECE HAD BELONGED PERSONALLY TO GRAY, UNTIL IT WAS PRESENTED AT SOTHEBY'S PARKE BERNET AUCTION IN MONTE CARLO IN 1980. IT WAS ORIGINALLY DESIGNED FOR CAR DESIGNER JEAN-HENRI LABOURDETTE AND WAS OFFERED BY GALERIE JEAN DÉSSERT TO COMPLEMENT HIS COLLECTION OF AFRICAN ART.

PROVENANCE:

ORIGINALLY PART OF EILEEN GRAY'S PERSONAL COLLECTION, THE ARMCHAIR WAS KEPT AT BOTH HER ICONIC RESIDENCE, VILLA E-1027 IN ROQUEBRUNE-CAP-MARTIN, AND LATER IN HER APARTMENT ON THE RUE BONAPARTE, PARIS. RETAINED BY GRAY THROUGHOUT HER LIFETIME, THE PIECE REMAINED IN HER POSSESSION UNTIL IT WAS OFFERED AT THE SOTHEBY'S PARKE BERNET SALE IN MONTE CARLO IN 1980.

LITERATURE:

PETER ADAM, 'EILEEN GRAY: ARCHITECT/DESIGNER' (NEW YORK: HARRY N. ABRAMS INC, 2000), 124-125 PETER ADAM, 'EILEEN GRAY: LEBEN UND WERK' (MUNICH: SCHIRMER/MOSEL, 2009), 287. THIS SPECIFIC ARM CHAIR WAS EXHIBITED HERE: EILEEN GRAY, CENTRE GEORGES POMPIDOU, PARIS, FEBRUARY - MAY 2013. EILEEN GRAY, IRISH MUSEUM OF MODERN ART, DUBLIN, OCTOBER 2013 - JANUARY 2014.

EILEEN GRAY

"SAFARI CHAIR"

1932

ARMCHAIR

ROQUEBRUNE - CAP - MARTIN

MILL OWNERS ASSOCIATION
BUILDING

AHMEDABAD

AS LE CORBUSIER BELIEVED THAT BUILDINGS SHOULD TOUCH OUR SOULS, HIS BUILDINGS WERE IMBUED WITH A MUCH DEEPER MEANING. HIS WORK EXPRESSED A RICH AMBIVALENCE BETWEEN THE RATIONAL AND THE SPIRITUAL.

TEAK MASSIV AND VENEER
HIGH COURT OF CHANDIGARH
46 X 56.7 X 46.8 IN (117 X 144 X 119 CM)

THE "HARMONIC SPIRAL", A COILED, SHELL-LIKE DIAGRAM THAT ARTICULATES A SERIES OF DECREASING MEASUREMENTS RELATING TO THE PROPORTIONS OF MODULOR MAN, IS A VISUAL DEVICE LE CORBUSIER REFERENCES THROUGHOUT HIS OEUVRE, BOTH IN BUILT AND PAINTED WORK.

AT CHANDIGARH, HE PRESENTS US WITH PERHAPS THE PUREST INTERPRETATION OF THIS SPIRAL FORM NOW AS A FUNCTIONAL OBJECT, IN THE SHAPE OF THE WITNESS BOX. THIS EXCEPTIONAL PIECE STEMS DIRECTLY FROM GOLDEN SECTION PROPORTIONS, BEING GENERATED FROM A PLAN EXTRUSION OF THE HARMONIC SPIRAL. THE CENTRIPETAL, SHELL-LIKE FORM ENCLOSES THE OCCUPANT WHILE ALSO CREATING A POWERFUL FOCUS TO THIS MISE-EN-SCÈNE. INTENDED SOLELY AS A WITNESS BOX, AND STRATEGICALLY POSITIONED UNDER THE INCLINED WEIGHT OF A PARASOL ROOF, AS IF TO IMPOSE THE ENTIRE WEIGHT OF THE BUILDING ONTO THE SHOULDER OF ITS OCCUPANT.

IT IS CLEAR FROM EVEN THE EARLIEST DRAWING PRODUCED IN PARIS THAT THE SPIRAL WAS CENTRAL TO HIS PLAN FOR THE COURTROOMS, AND IT REMAINED A CONSTANT FEATURE ACROSS VARIOUS ITERATIONS. THE FINAL COMPOSITION POSITIONS THE SPIRAL OF THE WITNESS BOX IN A STRICTLY ORTHOGONAL PLAN, EPITOMISING LE CORBUSIER'S OFTEN- USED TECHNIQUE OF JUXTAPOSING SCULPTURAL FORMS AND CURVES AGAINST AN OVERRIDING RECTILINEAR ORDER.¹

PROVENANCE:

CONCEIVED IN PARIS AND DEVELOPED THROUGH EARLY SCHEMATIC DRAWINGS FOR THE PALACE OF JUSTICE, CHANDIGARH, WITH THE HARMONIC SPIRAL FORMING A CENTRAL ELEMENT OF THE COURTROOM COMPOSITION; EXECUTED IN SITU IN INDIA AS PART OF THE CAPITOL COMPLEX UNDER LE CORBUSIER'S DIRECT SUPERVISION.

LITERATURE:

LE CORBUSIER, LE MODULOR, PARIS, 1948; LE CORBUSIER, LE MODULOR 2, PARIS, 1955; BOESIGER, W. (ED.), LE CORBUSIER: ŒUVRE COMPLÈTE 1946-1952, ZURICH, PP. 178-183; CURTIS, W. J. R., LE CORBUSIER: IDEAS AND FORMS, LONDON, PP. 192-195.

LE CORBUSIER

"LC-WITNESS BOX"

1955

WITNESS STAND

CHANDIGARH

HIGH COURT

CHANDIGARH

FLOORPLAN OF THE COURTOOM

MILL OWNERS' ASSOCIATION BUILDING AND VILLA SARABHAI, AHMEDABAD
LAQUERED STEEL AND ALUMINUM
16.5(H) X 21.5 X 5.5 IN (42 X 55 X 14 CM)

THIS WALL LIGHT WAS DESIGNED BY LE CORBUSIER AS A FACADE ELEMENT AND DONE IN STEEL AND IN ALUMINUM, WHICH WAS VERY AHEAD OF ITS TIME. THE SHAPE IS INSPIRED BY AIRPLANE WINGS. THE EXPRESSIVE AND DYNAMIC LAMP SHADE IS COMPETING WITH THE RIGID AND SYMMETRICAL FRAME STRUCTURE OF THE HOLDER. IT EXPRESSES SIMPLICITY; THE SHEET OF THE LAMP SHADE IS HUMBLE AND INDUSTRIAL, LOOKING FOR A CHARMING NORMALITY. ON THE OTHER HAND, IT HAS THESE SCULPTURAL QUALITIES, WHICH GIVE THAT ITEM AN UNEXPLAINED AURA.

A SIMILAR VERSION BUT WITHOUT HOLDERS WAS FIRST USED IN 1949 IN THE LE CORBUSIER- DESIGNED UNITÉ D'HABITATION BUILDING IN MARSEILLE. THIS VERSION WAS DONE IN 1954 FOR THE MILL OWNERS' ASSOCIATION BUILDING AND THE VILLA SARABHAI IN AHMEDABAD, INDIA.

THE SURFACE IS IN ITS ORIGINAL STATE; IT HAS NOT BEEN REPAINTED. THE ELECTRICITY HAS BEEN REDONE.

PROVENANCE:

PRODUCED IN FRANCE BY GUILUX (PLAN FLC P 1-11-92) OR IN INDIA FOR THE MILL OWNERS' ASSOCIATION AND THE VILLA SARABHAI, AHMEDABAD.

LITERATURE:

LE CORBUSIER FURNITURE AND INTERIORS, 1905-1965, RÜEGG, P. 351; LE CORBUSIER PIERRE JEANNERET, CHANDIGARH, INDIA, GALERIE PATRICK SEGUIN, P. 136.

LE CORBUSIER

"LC-III"

1960

WALL LAMP

AHMEDABAD

DESIGNED FOR LE CABANON, VERSION TEAK FOR CHANDIGARH
SOLID TEAK
13(H) X 17 X 10.5 IN (33 X 43 X 27 CM)

THIS STOOL WAS ORIGINALLY PRODUCED FOR LE CORBUSIER'S HOLIDAY HOUSE, LE CABANON, IN ROQUEBRUNE-CAP-MARTIN IN 1952. IT'S A SMALL HOUSE WITH A SIZE OF 3.66M X 3.66M (NOW DEFINED AS A UNESCO WORLD HERITAGE SITE). HE HAD PREVIOUSLY USED THE DESIGN FOR A SKETCH IN 1951. THIS OBJECT WAS DESIGNED TO BE A MULTIFUNCTIONAL ITEM – A STOOL/STEP, AND SIDE TABLE. THERE WERE SEVERAL VERSIONS. THE FIRST WAS MADE IN CHESTNUT WOOD FOR LE CABANON. THEN A LOW-COST VERSION WITH GREY PAINTED SURFACES FOR THE UNITÉ D'HABITATION IN NANTES-REZÉ. LATER, WITH A LARGE AMOUNT OF WOOD FOR THE PAVILLON DU BRÉSIL IN PARIS AND FOR THE "HEIDI WEBER HOUSE" IN ZURICH TOO, IT BECAME AN IMPORTANT ITEM DURING HIS LATE WORK. LE CORBUSIER PREFERRED TO USE THEM IN HIS RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS, GIVING THE FURNITURE A FLEXIBILITY, MAKING IT EASY TO MOVE, AND EXPRESSING A SPECIFIC NONCHALANCE. THEY WERE CUSTOM MADE FOR SPECIFIC PROJECTS AND WERE NOT AVAILABLE FOR SALE ANYWHERE ELSE, WHICH MAKES THEM VERY RARE. THE ARCHITECTURE OFFICE OF LE CORBUSIER IN CHANDIGARH DECIDED TO USE THEM IN THE STUDENT HOSTELS TOO.

THE LC-14 WAS PRODUCED IN TWO SIZES. BOTH MATCH THE STANDARDIZED LE CORBUSIER "LE MODULOR" DIMENSIONS: 43 X 33 X 27 CM AND 43 X 33 X 43 CM. IT IS A SIMPLE AND SMART ITEM. ITS BASIC SHAPE CREATES AN ARCHETYPAL EXPRESSION, REDUCING THE IDEA OF A SEAT TO IT'S ESSENCE.

THE HOLES ARE USED AS HANDLES, AND THE CORNERS HAVE DENTED JOINTS FOR ADDITIONAL STABILITY.

PROVENANCE:

STUDENT HOSTELS, CHANDIGARH, INDIA.

LITERATURE:

LE CORBUSIER: FURNITURE AND INTERIORS, 1905-1965, RÜEGG, P. 337; DOMUS IV, 1955-1959, FIELL AND FIELL, P.107-111; CH-DSGN, ED. SCALA, 2024.

EXHIBITIONS: T

HIS SPECIFIC ITEM WAS EXHIBITED AT THE NATIONAL MUSEUM OF THE SULTANATE OF OMAN IN 2023.

LE CORBUSIER

"LC-14"

CA. 1959

BOX STOOL

ROQUEBRUNE - CAP - MARTIN

"LE CABANON"

ROQUEBRUNE - CAP - MARTIN

MILL OWNERS' ASSOCIATION BUILDING, AHMEDABAD
SOLID TEAK
30(H) X 74.5 X 28 IN (76.5 X 189 X 71 CM)

THIS CONSOLE/DESK HAS BEEN DESIGNED BY B. DOSHI (WHO WON THE REPUTABLE PRITZKER PRIZE IN 2018) UNDER THE DIRECTION OF LE CORBUSIER. IT WAS DESIGNED FOR THE MILL OWNERS' ASSOCIATION BUILDING IN AHMEDABAD, INDIA. THE TOP HAS A SLIGHTLY LOWER NICHE. THE LEGS ARE WING-SHAPED. THAT CREATES A BALANCE BETWEEN THE SCULPTURAL TABLETOP AND THE AERODYNAMIC-APPEARING, ROUNDED LEGS, GIVING THE TABLE A STRONG CHARACTER. EVERYTHING IS MADE FROM SOLID TEAK. EACH PART IS STILL ORIGINAL. THE OBJECT HAS BEEN CAREFULLY RESTORED, AND THE SURFACES HAVE BEEN REFRESHED, KEEPING THE ORIGINAL PATINA. LE CORBUSIER DECIDED TO USE THIS DESIGN FOR HIS HOSPITAL PROJECT IN CHANDIGARH, TOO. THE DESK IS ALSO AVAILABLE IN A BLACK PAINT FINISH AND TEAK, WITH THE LATTER BEING AN EXTREMELY RARE TO FIND.

PROVENANCE:

CHANDIGARH HOSPITAL; PRIVATE COLLECTION.

LITERATURE:

LE CORBUSIER PIERRE JEANNERET, CHANDIGARH, INDIA, ED. GALERIE
PATRICK SEGUIN, 2014, P. 258, 288; LE CORBUSIER PIERRE JEANNERET, L'AVENTURE INDIENNE, ED. GOURCUFF
GRADENIGO, 2010, P. 498, 609; CH-DSGN, ED. SCALA, 2024.

EXHIBITIONS:

THIS SPECIFIC ITEM WAS EXHIBITED AT THE NATIONAL MUSEUM OF THE SULTANATE OF OMAN IN 2023.

LE CORBUSIER

"LC/BD-01-A"

CA. 1960

DESK-BOOKCASE

AHMEDABAD

THE GANDHI CENTRE,
PUNJAB UNIVERSITY

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET'S INTERESTS LAY MORE IN EXPERIMENTATION THAN IN SUCCESS, AND CHANDIGARH AFFORDED HIM THE OPPORTUNITY TO PLAY AND BREAK AWAY FROM THE EUROPEAN ARCHITECTURAL DOGMA.

RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS, CHANDIGARH
SOLID SISSOO AND STEEL
34.5(H) X 19 X 20.5 IN (88 X 48 X 52 CM)

THIS CHAIR COMES FROM THE EARLY FURNITURE DEVELOPMENT PHASE IN CHANDIGARH, WHEN PIERRE JEANNERET WAS STILL EXPERIMENTING IN ALL DIRECTIONS, TRYING TO FIND THE RIGHT VOCABULARY AND LOGIC FOR THE FURNITURE ITEMS IN CHANDIGARH. THIS IS PROBABLY HIS MOST INNOVATIVE TIME IN INDIA. IT IS THE ONLY ITEM WHERE HE TRIED TO ADAPT THE WOOD OF THE SEAT TO THE SHAPE OF THE HUMAN BODY. ADDITIONALLY, THERE ARE CUT-OUTS FOR THE STEEL RODS, REQUIRING A HIGH LEVEL OF TECHNICAL SKILLS FROM THE CARPENTER. SISSOO IS A VERY HARD WOOD, SO THIS DESIGN WAS NOT SUITABLE FOR LARGE-SCALE PRODUCTION. THEREFORE, ONLY A VERY FEW OF THEM WERE PRODUCED. THE APPROACH IS UNUSUAL AND POETIC AT THE SAME TIME. A SINGLE METAL ROD COILS LIKE A SNAKE AND PENETRATES THE SEAT AND BACKREST, CREATING A SCULPTURAL OBJECT. THE SIDE OF THE SEAT IS REMARKABLE, WHERE THE METAL ROD PENETRATES TWICE AND THEN CONTINUES AT A 45° ANGLE, BECOMING THE BASE OF THE CHAIR. A WONDERFUL PLAY IS FORMED BETWEEN THE SOLID, HEAVY WOOD AND THE ALMOST IMMATERIAL, LIGHT METAL ROD.

PROVENANCE:

RESIDENTIAL BUILDING, CHANDIGARH.

LITERATURE:

CH-DSGN, ED. SCALA, 2024; LE CORBUSIER PIERRE JEANNERET, L'AVENTURE INDIENNE, ED. GOURCUFF GRADENIGO, 2010, P. 557; CH-DSGN, ED. SCALA, 2023.

EXHIBITIONS:

THIS SPECIFIC ITEM WAS EXHIBITED AT THE NATIONAL MUSEUM OF THE SULTANATE OF OMAN IN 2023.

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-RARE-CHAIR"

CA. 1956

ARMCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

HIGH COURT OR SECRETARIAT, SECTOR 1, CHANDIGARH
186,000 USD
SOLID TEAK AND TEAK VENEER
30(H) X 136.5 X 54.5 IN (76 X 347 X 138 CM)

THICK TABLETOP, ANGLED, WITH TWO FEET IN A V-SHAPE AND A CENTRAL FOOT WITH TWO NICHES. LE CORBUSIER DESIGNED ONLY A FEW FURNITURE OBJECTS FOR CHANDIGARH. IN SECTOR 1 OF THE CAPITOL, HE UNDERTOOK THIS TASK FOR THE MOST IMPORTANT INTERIORS. THIS TABLE IS CHARACTERIZED BY A VERY EXPRESSIVE FORM. WITH VERY SIMPLE GESTURES, THE TABLE IS GIVEN A SCULPTURAL QUALITY AND, AT THE SAME TIME MONUMENTAL DIMENSIONS. ALL PARTS, INCLUDING THE SCREWS, ARE ORIGINAL AND HAVE NOT BEEN REPLACED. THIS IS A LATE MASTERPIECE BY LE CORBUSIER.

PROVENANCE:

HIGH COURT, CHANDIGARH; PRIVATE COLLECTION.

LITERATURE:

LE CORBUSIER, PIERRE JEANNERET: L'AVENTURE INDIENNE, DESIGN -ART - ARCHITECTURE, TOUCHALEAUME AND MOREAU, P. 579-580.

EXHIBITIONS:

THIS SPECIFIC ITEM WAS EXHIBITED AT THE NATIONAL MUSEUM OF THE SULTANATE OF OMAN IN 2023.

LE CORBUSIER

"LC-TAT-07-A"

1957 - 1958

MINISTER'S DESK

CHANDIGARH

PRIVATE RESIDENCES, GENERAL HOSPITAL ENTRANCE HALL
SOLID TEAK AND CANE
23.50(H) X 60.25 X 30.25 IN (60 X 153 X 77 CM)

THIS ITEM IS THE RARE THREE-SEATER VERSION OF THE EASY CHAIR CALLED THE KANGAROO CHAIR, WHICH IS THE MOST ICONIC ONE OF ALL CHANDIGARH ITEMS. THE SILHOUETTE IS CLEAR AND HAS THE FLOWING SHAPE OF A WAVE. THE OUTLINE GETS WIDER AND THINNER, GIVING THE CHAIR A DYNAMIC FEEL. THE STRONG WOOD FRAME AND THE THIN CANING CREATE A NICE CONTRAST. ROUNDED CORNERS AND CURVED BEAMS GIVE THE SHAPE ADDITIONAL SOFTNESS. WHILE MOST ITEMS PRODUCED IN CHANDIGARH HAD ANGULAR WOODEN PARTS, SHOWING HOW SIMPLE WOODEN PIECES CAN BE CONNECTED, THIS BENCH HAS ROUNDED EDGES AND MORE COMPLEX JOINTS. THE SLIGHTLY MOULDED BACKSEAT SHOWS A SLIGHTLY ORGANIC QUALITY. THE VERTICAL WOODEN ELEMENTS ARE REMINISCENT OF A SPINE.

PROVENANCE:

RESIDENTIAL BUILDING, CHANDIGARH.

LITERATURE:

LE CORBUSIER PIERRE JEANNERET, CHANDIGARH, INDIA, GALERIE PATRICK SEGUIN, P. 204-205; LE CORBUSIER, PIERRE JEANNERET: L'AVENTURE INDIENNE, DESIGN-ART-ARCHITECTURE, TOUCHALEAUME AND MOREAU, P. 570-571.

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-59-B"

1955 / 1964

KANGAROO SOFA

CHANDIGARH

PANJAB UNIVERSITY LIBRARY, CHANDIGARH
SOLID TEAK AND ALUMINUM
65.5(H) X 60 X 18.5 IN (167 X 152 X 47 CM)

THIS COMMITTEE CONFERENCE TABLE IS KNOWN AS THE "BOOMERANG TABLE". THE LEGS ARE THE CHARACTERISTIC ELEMENT OF THAT TABLE. THEY HAVE THE SHAPE OF TWO CROSSING, BOOMERANG-SHAPED BOWS. IN HIS LATER WORK, LE CORBUSIER LOVED TO INTEGRATE ELEMENTS OF HIS PHILOSOPHY INTO THE SHAPE. THERE WERE SYMBOLIC ELEMENTS HE STARTED TO ADD, GIVING HIS ITEMS A DEEPER MEANING. LE CORBUSIER HAD LONG SINCE LEFT THE PATH OF A PRAGMATIC AND FUNCTIONAL MINDSET AND BECAME MORE FOCUSED ON THE MYSTICAL AND SPIRITUALISTIC ASPECTS. SO, INDIA WAS THE PERFECT INSPIRATION TO EXPRESS HIS IDEAS OF A COSMIC TRUTH. THAT IS ONE OF THE FEW PIECES OF DESIGN LE CORBUSIER DESIGNED FOR CHANDIGARH. IT IS ONE OF THE FEW TABLES THAT STILL HAS THE ORIGINAL TOP VENEER, WHICH IN MOST CASES GOT REPLACED OVER TIME. THE CURVED LEGS OF THE TABLE DIRECTLY ECHO THE CURVE OF THE DAILY PATH OF THE SUN ("LE JEU DU SOLEIL", FRENCH), PICTURED ON THE ENTRANCE DOOR OF THE ASSEMBLY BUILDING IN CHANDIGARH.

PROVENANCE:

ASSEMBLY BUILDING, SECTOR 1, CHANDIGARH.

LITERATURE:

LE CORBUSIER, PIERRE JEANNERET: L'AVENTURE INDIENNE, ERIC TOUCHALEAUME AND GERALD MOREAU, 2010, P. 246-47, 582.

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-R-26-A"

SOLID TEAK, ALUMINIUM

1960

BOOK CASE FOR PERIODICALS

CHANDIGARH

TOM STRALA

B. 1974

FURNITURE DOESN'T NEED TO BEHAVE LIKE A CONSUMER GOOD SIMPLY BECAUSE IT SERVES A PRACTICAL FUNCTION. AS A DESIGNER, TOM STRALA EMBODIES FREEDOM AND EXPLORES EVERY FACET OF THIS EXISTENTIAL THEME.

POWDER COATED ALUMINIUM
25.5(H) X 23.5 X 23.5 IN (65 X 60 X 60 CM)
SOLID TEAK AND CANE

THIS CEILING LAMP IS FROM A LIMITED SERIES (3/125). A LIGHT RING ATTACHED TO A BULKY AND CLUMSY RECTANGULAR PLASTIC. IT IS THE FIRST ENERGY-SAVING BULB WITH AN ELECTRIC CONTROL GEAR AND THE USUAL BULB SOCKET FROM 1983. CALMARES MULTIPLIES THIS MISSHAPED ENERGY-SAVING BULB 13 TIMES AND TRANSFORMS ITS ABSURD CIRCULAR SHAPE INTO A CHANDELIER. THERE IS A CONFUSING COLLISION BETWEEN THE UGLINESS OF EVERYDAY BANALITY AND THE ELEGANCE OF THE BOURGEOIS CHANDELIER TYPE. A TRIBUTE TO BANALITY AND A CRITIQUE OF THE FLIGHT INTO NOSTALGIA.

PROVENANCE:
TOM STRALA STUDIO, ZURICH, SWITZERLAND.
LITERATURE:
THE RADICALISM OF BANALITY, P! GALERIE, 2023.

TOM STRALA

"CALMARES"

03 OF 125

2010 - 2012

LAMP

ZURICH

LIMITED EDITION, SWITZERLAND, ZURICH
CONCRETE AND REINFORCING BARS
12.25(H) X 82 X 37.75 IN (31 X 208 X 96 CM)

TOM STRALA PRODUCES THEM AS MUCH AS POSSIBLE HIMSELF. HE DESIRES TO FULFIL HIS CURIOSITY AND PERSONALLY EXPERIENCE THE MATERIAL. ONLY IN THIS MANNER CAN A DESIGNER LEARN TO COMPREHEND AND DEVELOP. A METHOD THAT IS STILL KNOWN BY THE OLD MASTERS, IN WHICH DESIGN IS MORE THAN MERELY SATISFACTORY. EVERYTHING HERE IS CENTERED ON EXPERIMENTATION. THAT IS THE ONLY MODERN DESIGNER WE CONSIDER TO BE SUFFICIENTLY PROFOUND. THE TABLE HAS MONUMENTAL DIMENSIONS. IT NEVERTHELESS APPEARS LIGHT WITH THE LEGS, WHICH ARE ULTIMATELY THE REINFORCING IRONS FROM THE CONCRETE. VERY ESSENTIAL, BUT ALSO BANAL. THE TOP HAS THIS WONDERFUL CONCRETE SURFACE WHERE YOU CAN SEE THE PEBBLES AND LOOK AT THEM FOR HOURS. IT REMINDS US OF THE RYOAN-JI TEMPLE (KYOTO, 15TH-CENTURY ZEN GARDEN).

IT IS ALSO A RAW OBJECT THAT AVOIDS ANY DECORATIVE NONSENSE. EVERYDAY LIFE AND THE PRESENT SERVE AS INSPIRATION, WHERE THE REALITY OF BUILDING SITES IS BROUGHT TO THE CENTER. IN THIS WAY, IT REBELS AGAINST THE NOSTALGIC TENDENCIES IN CURRENT DESIGN.

PROVENANCE:

TOM STRALA STUDIO, ZURICH, SWITZERLAND.

LITERATURE:

THE RADICALISM OF BANALITY, P! GALLERY, ZURICH, 2023; CH-DSGN, SCALA, LONDON, 2023.

EXHIBITIONS:

THIS SPECIFIC ITEM WAS EXHIBITED AT THE NATIONAL MUSEUM OF THE SULTANATE OF OMAN IN 2023.

TOM STRALA

"TS-290KG"

2021

SIDE TABLE

ZURICH

PANJAB UNIVERSITY AND RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS
(AVAILABLE AS A PAIR) SOLID TEAK AND CANE
32(H) X 21.25 X 23 IN (81 X 54 X 59 CM)

FLOATING IS AN IMPORTANT DESIGN ELEMENT IN THIS ARMCHAIR. THE BACKREST IS ONLY CONNECTED TO THE SEAT BY THE SMALL LINK IN THE MIDDLE, MAKING THE BACKREST APPEAR TO BE HANGING IN THE AIR. THE L-SHAPED ARM PIECES REST AGAINST THIS FLOATING BACKREST AND CREATE A VISUALLY FRAGILE BALANCE. THE SHAPE IS EXPRESSIVE. THE L-SHAPE OF THE ARM PIECE AND THE L-SHAPE OF THE BACK LEG CROSS EACH OTHER. THIS SIMPLE FORMAL LANGUAGE EMPHASIZES THE SCULPTURAL QUALITY.

PROVENANCE:

RESIDENTIAL BUILDING IN CHANDIGARH; PRIVATE COLLECTION.

LITERATURE:

LE CORBUSIER, PIERRE JEANNERET: L'AVENTURE INDIENNE, ERIC TOUCHALEAUME AND GERALD MOREAU, 2010, P. 571;
CATALOGUE RAISONNÉ DU MOBILIER JEANNERET CHANDIGARH", JACQUES DWORCZAK, ASSOULINE, 2019, P. 115,329.

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-62-A"

CA. 1960

ARMCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

MANUFACTURED BY G.A.V.D. GROENEKAN, DE BUIL, NETHERLANDS
PAINTED WOOD AND ALUMINUM | 34(H) X 26 X 31 IN (86 X 66 X 79 CM)

THE CHAIR WAS MADE BY HIS CRAFTSMEN FROM THE NETHERLANDS, G.A.V.D. GROENEKAN AND DE BILT, WHO WORKED UNDER HIS DIRECTION FROM 1917 TO 1951. IT REPRESENTS ONE OF THE FIRST DESIGNS DONE BY THE DE STIJL ART MOVEMENT. THE DE STIJL ART MOVEMENT WAS FOUNDED IN THE NETHERLANDS AS A REACTION AGAINST THE HORRORS OF WORLD WAR I. THE VISUAL LANGUAGE OF THE MOVEMENT CONSISTED OF GEOMETRIC FORMS AND PRIMARY COLORS, WHICH WERE USED TO FIND HARMONY AND BALANCE AGAINST THE CHAOTIC WORLD EVENTS OF THAT TIME. THE CHAIR WAS ORIGINALLY DESIGNED IN 1917 BUT NOT PAINTED IN PRIMARY COLORS (RED, BLUE AND YELLOW). THAT CAME AFTER 1923. RIETVELD BELIEVED THAT THERE WAS A GREATER GOAL FOR THE FURNITURE DESIGNER THAN JUST PHYSICAL COMFORT: THE WELL-BEING AND COMFORT OF THE SPIRIT. SOME OF THE FIRST CHAIR PRODUCTIONS WERE MADE FOR THE "RIETVELD SCHRÖDER HOUSE" IN UTRECHT, NETHERLANDS, ALSO DESIGNED BY HIM IN 1924. LATER, IT WAS CONVERTED INTO A MUSEUM AND LISTED AS A UNESCO WORLD HERITAGE SITE.

THE CHAIR HAS A FRAME OF BLACK WOOD BEAMS. IT IS AN ABSTRACT SPATIAL STRUCTURE IN WHICH THE RED AND BLUE PANELS ARE MOUNTED. SPATIAL QUALITIES AND THE MENTAL RATHER THAN THE PRAGMATIC ARE SOUGHT HERE. THIS SPECIFIC CHAIR HAS ITS ORIGINAL PAINT AND HAS NEVER BEEN REPAINTED. IT IS ONE OF THE FEW ORIGINALS THAT STILL EXIST.

PROVENANCE:

ACQUIRED DIRECTLY FROM GERRIT RIETVELD BY MR. AND MRS. ENGELS, CURAÇAO; AUCTION, 2022; PRIVATE COLLECTION.

LITERATURE:

THE COMPLETE RIETVELD FURNITURE, VÖGE, P. 58-59; GERRIT RIETVELD: THE COMPLETE WORKS 1888-1964, KUPER AND VAN ZIJL, P. 74-76.

GERRIT RIETVELD

"RED AND BLUE"

CA. 1923 - 1951

ARMCHAIR

DE BILT

THE SCHRÖDER HOUSE

UTRECHT

RIETVELD BELIEVED HIS PRECISE GEOMETRY AND OPEN STRUCTURES OFFERED TRUE UNIVERSALITY. HIS SUSPECTED COMMUNIST SYMPATHIES MAY EXPLAIN WHY HE RECEIVED NO SUPPORT AFTER THE WAR.

ASSEMBLY BUILDING, CHANDIGARH
SOLID TEAK WITH TEAK VENEER
29.5(H) X 95.5 X 47.5 IN (75 X 243 X 121 CM)

THIS COMMITTEE CONFERENCE TABLE IS KNOWN AS THE "BOOMERANG TABLE". THE LEGS ARE THE CHARACTERISTIC ELEMENT OF THAT TABLE. THEY HAVE THE SHAPE OF TWO CROSSING, BOOMERANG-SHAPED BOWS. IN HIS LATER WORK, LE CORBUSIER LOVED TO INTEGRATE ELEMENTS OF HIS PHILOSOPHY INTO THE SHAPE. THERE WERE SYMBOLIC ELEMENTS HE STARTED TO ADD, GIVING HIS ITEMS A DEEPER MEANING. LE CORBUSIER HAD LONG SINCE LEFT THE PATH OF A PRAGMATIC AND FUNCTIONAL MINDSET AND BECAME MORE FOCUSED ON THE MYSTICAL AND SPIRITUALISTIC ASPECTS. SO, INDIA WAS THE PERFECT INSPIRATION TO EXPRESS HIS IDEAS OF A COSMIC TRUTH. THAT IS ONE OF THE FEW PIECES OF DESIGN LE CORBUSIER DESIGNED FOR CHANDIGARH. IT IS ONE OF THE FEW TABLES THAT STILL HAS THE ORIGINAL TOP VENEER, WHICH IN MOST CASES GOT REPLACED OVER TIME. THE CURVED LEGS OF THE TABLE DIRECTLY ECHO THE CURVE OF THE DAILY PATH OF THE SUN ("LE JEU DU SOLEIL", FRENCH), PICTURED ON THE ENTRANCE DOOR OF THE ASSEMBLY BUILDING IN CHANDIGARH.

PROVENANCE:
ASSEMBLY BUILDING, SECTOR 1, CHANDIGARH.

LITERATURE:
LE CORBUSIER, PIERRE JEANNERET: L'AVENTURE INDIENNE, ERIC TOUCHALEAUME AND GERALD MOREAU, 2010, P. 246-47, 582.

LE CORBUSIER
PIERRE JEANNERET

"LC/PJ-TAT-14-A"

1963 - 1964

BOOMERANG TABLE

CHANDIGARH

HIGH COURT

CHANDIGARH

CITÉ CANSADO, MAURITANIA
OAK, PAINTED STEEL AND MASONITE
30.25(H) X 99 X 18 IN (77 X 251.5 X 46 CM)

STORAGE WAS A VITAL ISSUE FOR CHARLOTTE PERRIAND, WHO BELIEVED THAT LIFE WAS NOT POSSIBLE WITHOUT RATIONAL STORAGE DESIGNED FOR SMALLER, MODERN HOMES. PERRIAND'S OPINION WAS THAT THE PEOPLE OWNED FAR TOO MANY THINGS AND TOO MUCH FURNITURE. SHE THOUGHT THAT WE ACCUMULATED OBJECTS TO GIVE THE IMPRESSION OF WEALTH AND DIDN'T AGREE WITH THAT IDEA. THAT'S HOW PERRIAND'S APPROACH WAS THE OPPOSITE OF DECORATION. HER INTENTION WAS TO CREATE EMPTINESS TO CREATE SPACE. THAT'S HOW THE MODULAR SYSTEM, CREATED BY HER AND EMBODIED IN HER DESIGNS, SEEMED TO BE THE ANSWER TO HER OWN QUESTIONS.

THE HISTORY OF THIS TYPE OF BAHUT STARTED AROUND 1958. THEY HAVE BEEN PRODUCED BY NÉGRONI AND MÉTAL MEUBLE FOR GALERIE STEPH SIMON IN PARIS, FRANCE. THERE WERE DIFFERENT TYPES OF LEGS, SOME MADE OF WOOD AND SOME PAINTED IN COLOR. THE MODEL FOR CANSADO IN MAURITANIA HAS BEEN PRODUCED WITH METAL LEGS. CANSADO IS A SETTLEMENT WITH 750 HOUSES FOR THE IRON MINE WORKERS OF THE ASSOCIATION MIFERMA, DESIGNED BY THE ARCHITECT JEAN DIMITIJEVIC AND BUILT BETWEEN 1959 AND 1963. CHARLOTTE PERRIAND WAS RESPONSIBLE FOR DESIGNING THE INTERIORS. THE WOOD IS OAK, THE STRUCTURE IS ENAMELED STEEL AND ALUMINUM, AND THE SLIDING DOORS ARE MADE OF MASONITE. THE ROUND RIVET-SHAPED SCREWS ARE A TYPICAL ELEMENT OF JEAN PROUVÉ ITEMS AND HAVE BEEN DESIGNED BY HIS ATELIER, WITH WHOM CHARLOTTE PERRIAND HAD A VERY CLOSE COLLABORATION. THERE WERE VERSIONS WITH TWO, THREE, FOUR, OR FIVE SLIDING DOORS.

PROVENANCE:

SETTLEMENT FOR MIFERMA, CANSADO; NOUAKCHOTT, MAURITANIA.

LITERATURE:

JACQUES BARSAC, CHARLOTTE PERRIAND, UN ART D'HABITER, 1903-1959, PARIS, 2005, P. 440-42; A STEPH SIMON PROSPECTUS, FRANÇOIS LAFFANOUR; STEPH SIMON RETROSPECTIVE, 1956-1974: PROUVÉ, PERRIAND, MOUILLE, JOUVE, NOGUCHI, EXH. CAT., GALERIE DOWNTOWN, PARIS, 2007, P. 67.

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"BAHUT-5"

1950

BUFFET WITH FIVE SLIDING
DOORS

CANSADO

CASCADE RESIDENCE, 1967-1969

LES ARCS 1600

PERRIAND WAS A FREE-SPIRITED LEFTIST, WHO, IN HER SEARCH FOR INDIVIDUAL EXPRESSION, ABANDONED THE TRADITIONAL ARCHITECTURAL DOCTRINE IN FAVOUR OF A MORE EMOTIONAL AND POETIC LANGUAGE.

BRAZZAVILLE, CONGO
SOLID DIBETOU WOOD
28.5(H) X 93 X 42 IN (72.5 X 236 X 107 CM)

THE TABLE KNOWN AS FORME LIBRE WAS THE PRICIEST PIECE OF FURNITURE BY CHARLOTTE PERRIAND THAT WAS EVER SOLD BY THE GALERIE STEPH SIMON. TO ITS EXTREMELY HIGH RETAIL PRICE (170,000 FRANCS IN 1957), THE CLIENT COULD ADD LONG DELIVERY DELAYS, LARGELY DUE TO THE DIFFICULTY IN PROCURING A SUPPLY OF QUALITY WOOD. BUT THE GALERIE STEPH SIMON OFFERED A SPECIAL TREAT TO ITS BUYERS: THE CARPENTER ANDRÉ CHETAÏLLE WOULD CRAFT THEIR TABLE. THAT INFORMATION – A FACT THAT WAS NEVER MENTIONED ON ANY OFFICIAL DOCUMENT OR ANY PRICE QUOTATION – WAS BY ITSELF A PLEDGE OF QUALITY BECAUSE ANY PIECE OF FURNITURE PRODUCED BY CHETAÏLLE'S WORKSHOP WAS GUARANTEED TO BE EXACTINGLY FAITHFUL TO BOTH THE DESIGN AND THE SPIRIT OF PERRIAND. ANY PIECE CRAFTED BY CHETAÏLLE ALSO CARRIED THE ASSURANCE THAT IT WAS MADE FROM THE MOST NOBLE OF WOOD SPECIES, AND THAT THE WOOD'S LONG DRYING TIME - SOMETIMES EXCEEDING TEN YEARS - WOULD BE SUCH THAT, OVER TIME, IT WOULD NOT CRACK EVEN A LITTLE BIT. PERRIAND ADMIRERED HIS EXCEPTIONAL KNOW-HOW, AND WITH HIM, PERRIAND ALSO SHARED A PASSION FOR WOOD.

"THE SHAPES OF MY TABLES [...] DEPENDED ON THE LENGTH OF THE WOOD LOGS".

THE WOOD LENGTH DICTATED THE PROPORTIONS IN THE FLUID AND ELEGANT DESIGN PRODUCED BY PERRIAND. TRUE TO HER LOVE OF FORM, PERRIAND GAVE HER TABLE AN INVITING SHAPE SO THAT IT WOULD BRING HER GUESTS TOGETHER AROUND IT AND DRAW THEIR EYES TO THE CENTER OF THE TABLE. THE SIMPLE SHAPE OF THE TABLE CONCEALED THE COMPLEXITY OF PERRIAND'S DESIGN. THE EXPERT HANDS OF CHETAÏLLE TOOK CARE OF THE REST. AS A TRULY ARTFUL CARPENTER, HE ASSEMBLED THE WOODEN PLANKS WITH SPLINE JOINTS, DELIBERATELY LEAVING THE ASSEMBLY DETAILS VISIBLE. THE EXCEPTIONAL THICKNESS WAS CARVED OUT OF DIBETOU MAHAGONY. PERRIAND ACKNOWLEDGED THAT CHETAÏLLE'S TALENT AND SIGNATURE MAGNIFIED HER OWN FINEST CREATIONS.

PROVENANCE:

AIR FRANCE EMPLOYEE'S BUILDING IN BRAZZAVILLE, CONGO.

LITERATURE:

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND, UN ART D'HABITER, BARSAC, P. 437-439; STEPH SIMON: RETROSPECTIVE 1956-1974, LAFFANOUR, P. 68-71.

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"FORME LIBRE"

1957

TABLE

BRAZZAVILLE

CITÉ CANSADO, MAURITANIA
OAK OR MAHOGANY AND METAL
27.75(H) X 110 X 13.25 IN (70.5 X 280 X 34 CM)

THE NUAGE ("CLOUD" IN FRENCH) APPEARS TO FLOAT, AS IF DRIVEN BY THE WIND. MADE OF A THIN METAL SHEET AND LONG WOODEN BOARDS, SIMPLE AND MODULARLY ASSEMBLED. IT WORKS AS A MOUNTABLE STRUCTURE, WITH THE SHAPE AND SIZE ADAPTABLE TO THE NEEDS OF EACH USER. CONNECTED WITH ROUND RIVET-SHAPED SCREWS THAT WERE DESIGNED AND PRODUCED BY JEAN PROUVÉ.

FOR CHARLOTTE PERRIAND, STORAGE OBJECTS WERE VERY IMPORTANT. SHE SPENT HER ENTIRE CAREER PONDERING THE QUESTION OF HOW TO BEST INTEGRATE STORAGE SPACES INTO HER INTERIOR DESIGN. IN HER MANIFESTO "UN ART D'HABITER" (1950), SHE WROTE: "WHAT IS THE MOST ESSENTIAL ELEMENT IN HOUSEHOLD AMENITIES? LET'S ANSWER WITHOUT HESITATION: STORAGE SPACE. WITHOUT WELL-CONCEIVED STORAGE, EMPTY SPACES ARE UNTHINKABLE IN A DWELLING".

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND IS FINALLY THE MOTHER OF THE FLEXIBLE AND MODULAR IKEA CONCEPT, SO THE NUAGE IS SIMPLE TO ASSEMBLE AND REARRANGE.

PROVENANCE:

CITÉ CANSADO, MAURITANIA; PRIVATE COLLECTION.

LITERATURE:

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND, UN ART D'HABITER, BARSAC, P. 420-423 ILLUSTRATED VARIATIONS.

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"NUAGE"

1958

WALL-MOUNTED SHELF WITH 3
LEVELS

CANSADO

ADMINISTRATIVE BUILDINGS AND RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS, CHANDIGARH
SOLID TEAK AND UPHOLSTERY
17.75(H) X 74 X 36.50 IN (45 X 188 X 93 CM)

THE DAYBED IS REDUCED TO SIMPLE GEOMETRICAL ELEMENTS: THE A-SHAPED LEGS AND THE SQUARE SEATING SURFACE ON IT. NOT MORE, NOT LESS. THESE KINDS OF LEGS ARE TYPICAL OF MANY CHANDIGARH DESIGNS BY PIERRE JEANNERET. THEY ARE SLIGHTLY ROUNDED ON THE OUTER SIDE, AND SHARP ON THE INNER SIDE. THE UPHOLSTERY FOR THIS PIECE WAS DONE WITH CORD DESIGNED BY HEDI SLIMANE.

PROVENANCE:
RESIDENTIAL BUILDING, CHANDIGARH.

LITERATURE:
LE CORBUSIER, PIERRE JEANNERET: L'AVENTURE INDIENNE, ERIC TOUCHALEAUME AND GERALD MOREAU, 2010, P. 591.

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-L-12-A"

1957 - 1958

DAYBED

CHANDIGARH

SESC FÁBRICA POMPEIA

SÃO PAULO

BARDI WAS A COMMUNIST WHO REMAINED UNMISTAKABLY BOURGEOIS. FULL OF CONTRADICTIONS, SHE DISCOVERED HER OWN AESTHETIC AND ITS FREEDOM IN BRAZIL'S VERNACULAR CULTURE.

RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS, SAO PAULO, BRAZIL
WOOD, IRON AND UPHOLSTERY
29.50(H) X 26 X 28.25 IN (75 X 66 X 72 CM)

ARMCHAIR WAS DESIGNED BY ITALIAN-BRAZILIAN ARCHITECT AND DESIGNER LINA BO BARDI (1914-1992) AND GIANCARLO PALANTI FOR STUDIO D'ARTE PALMA. THE CHAIR IS MADE OF WOOD WITH UPHOLSTERED SEATS AND STANDS ON AN IRON HAIRPIN FRAME. THE COMBINATION OF THE METAL LEGS, THE WOODEN FRAME, AND THE UPHOLSTERY SHOWS A RADICAL APPROACH. IT IS NOT ABOUT TASTE CRITERIA, BUT RATHER ABOUT EXPERIMENTATION. THE PLAYFULNESS OF LINA BO BARDI'S APPROACH BECOMES VISIBLE HERE. SHOWING HOW SHE ENJOYS COMBINING DIFFERENT INFLUENCES, MATERIALS, SHAPES AND STYLES IN A VERY LIBERATED WAY.

AS AN ITALIAN-BORN ARCHITECT WHO SPENT MUCH OF HER LIFE IN BRAZIL, LINA BO BARDI INITIALLY WORKED FOR THE ARCHITECT AND DESIGNER GIO PONTI IN MILAN. AFTER WORLD WAR II, SHE LEFT WITH HER HUSBAND FOR A NEW LIFE IN SÃO PAULO, WHERE THEY SOON GOT ABSORBED INTO ARTISTIC AND INTELLECTUAL CIRCLES. HER EARLY WORK WAS QUITE MODERNIST IN STYLE; HOWEVER, THE ETHNIC AND EMOTIONAL ELEMENTS OF BRAZILIAN ARCHITECTURE AND LIFE GRADUALLY CAME TO INFLUENCE HER THINKING. MUCH OF HER DESIGN WORK WAS EXPERIMENTAL AS WELL AS SPIRITUAL IN CHARACTER AND INCLUDED BOTH SIMPLE HOUSES AND CONCRETE BRUTALIST BUILDINGS WITH LARGE DIMENSIONS. SHE WAS A COMMUNIST BUT REMAINED BOURGEOIS. FULL OF CONTRADICTIONS, SHE FOUND HER OWN AESTHETIC AND ITS FREEDOM.

PROVENANCE:

RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS, SAO PAULO, BRAZIL; PRIVATE COLLECTION, NYC.

LITERATURE:

BRAZIL MODERN, ARIC CHEN, 2016; RETROSPECTIVE AT R & COMPANY GALLERY, NEW YORK ON THE WORK OF LINA BO BARDI AND ROBERTO BURLE MARX, 2015.

LINA BO BARDI

"ARMCHAIR"

CA. 1953

ARMCHAIR

SÃO PAULO

HAUS AM HORN

WEIMAR

ALL HUMAN-CONTACT SURFACES WERE SOFTENED WITH WARMER, ORGANIC MATERIALS LIKE LEATHER, COTTON, WICKER, AND WOOD. BREUER ANTICIPATED ERGONOMIC DESIGN, KEEPING THE HUMAN BODY AT THE CENTER.

BAUHAUS, WEIMAR

OAK WOOD STAINED AND FABRIC

38(H) X 22 X 24.5 IN (96.5 X 56 X 62 CM)

A WOODEN-SLAT CHAIR CALLED "TI-1A" IS AN AUTHENTIC BAUHAUS ITEM DESIGNED BY MARCEL BREUER IN 1922-1924 AND CRAFTED AT THE BAUHAUS IN WEIMAR. BREUER WAS A MODERNIST ARCHITECT, SCULPTOR, AND FURNITURE DESIGNER, BEST KNOWN FOR THE DESIGN OF THE MOST ICONIC CHAIRS OF THE 20TH CENTURY. HE WAS ONE OF THE FIRST STUDENTS, PIONEERS, AND LATER THE TEACHER OF THE BAUHAUS MOVEMENT AS WELL AS THE INTERNATIONAL STYLE. THE WOODEN-SLAT CHAIR WAS MADE DURING BREUER'S FIRST YEARS AT THE BAUHAUS SCHOOL IN WEIMAR. ITS HEAD OF THE SCHOOL DEPARTMENTS, THE ARCHITECT WALTER GROPIUS, IMMEDIATELY RECOGNIZED BREUER'S TALENT AND PROMOTED HIM WITHIN A YEAR TO HEAD OF THE CARPENTRY SHOP. AT THE BAUHAUS, BREUER PRODUCED THE FURNITURE FOR GROPIUS' SOMMERFELD HOUSE IN BERLIN AS WELL AS HIS ACCLAIMED SERIES OF "AFRICAN" AND "SLATTED" CHAIRS. BREUER DID REMARKABLE DESIGN WORK WITH THIS WOODEN-SLAT CHAIR, WHERE HE USED A CANTILEVERED FRAME AS THE CONSTRUCTION METHOD FOR THE FIRST TIME. ADDITIONALLY, THE CHAIR SERVES AS A REMINDER OF SIGNIFICANT COLLABORATIONS BETWEEN BREUER AND THE GERMAN TEXTILE ARTIST GUNTA STÖLZL'S BAUHAUS WEAVING WORKSHOPS. WHILE THE FIRST VERSION OF 1922 STILL USED TWO DIFFERENT KINDS OF WOOD SLATS, SQUARE AND RECTANGULAR, THIS SECOND VERSION GOT MORE RADICAL AND USED EVERYTHING WITH THE SAME DIMENSION OF SLATS, EXPRESSING A MUCH STRONGER DYNAMIC IN THE SHAPE. THE CHAIR HAS A RIGID WOODEN STRUCTURE THAT IS SOFTENED BY THE WOVEN FABRIC, WHICH ALLOWS FOR A GENTLY SLOPING SEAT AND BACK.

PROVENANCE:

BAUHAUS SCHOOL, WEIMAR; AUCTION, 2022; PRIVATE COLLECTION.

LITERATURE:

CAT. BAUHAUS ARCHIVE BERLIN, THE COLLECTION, BERLIN 1987, P. 90.

MARCEL BREUER

"TI-1A CHAIR"

1922 - 1924

WOODEN-SLAT CHAIR

WEIMAR

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LISTED IN CHRONOLOGICAL ORDER AS THEY APPEAR IN THIS DOCUMENT

VILLA E-1027 BY EILEEN GRAY (WITH JEAN BADOVICI)

- INTERIOR LIVING / SLEEPING AREA

© ADAGP, P. XX (PHOTO ARCHIVES EILEEN GRAY / JACQUES BARSAC, PARIS)

PORTRAIT OF EILEEN GRAY

- STUDIO PHOTOGRAPH

© ESTATE OF EILEEN GRAY / ADAGP, P. XX (PHOTOGRAPHER UNKNOWN, PRIVATE COLLECTION; REPRODUCED IN EILEEN GRAY: ARCHITECT/DESIGNER, ACADEMY EDITIONS, LONDON)

MILL OWNERS' ASSOCIATION BUILDING (ATMA HOUSE) BY LE CORBUSIER

- EAST FAÇADE SEEN ACROSS THE SABARMATI RIVER, AHMEDABAD

© FLC/ADAGP, P. XX (PHOTO STUDIO INDIANO, ARCHIVES FONDATION LE CORBUSIER, PARIS)

PORTRAIT OF LE CORBUSIER

- HALF-LENGTH VIEW WITH PIPE AND ROUND SPECTACLES

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HIGH COURT BUILDING ON THE CAPITOL BY LE CORBUSIER

- COURT ROOM

© FLC/ADAGP P. 26 (PHOTOS STUDIO INDIANO.ARCHIVES ERIC TOUCHALEAUME, PARIS)

LE CORBUSIER IN THE CABANON DE CAP-MARTIN

© FLC/ADAGP, P. 132 (PHOTOS STUDIO INDIANO.ARCHIVES ERIC TOUCHALEAUME, PARIS)

PORTRAIT OF PIERRE JEANNERET

- LIKELY TAKEN IN CHANDIGARH, INDIA, BETWEEN 1951 AND 1965, DURING WORK ON THE CITY'S MASTERPLAN AND DESIGN WITH LE CORBUSIER

© PIERRE JEANNERET FONDS, GIFT OF JACQUELINE JEANNERET, CANADIAN CENTRE FOR ARCHITECTURE (REPRODUCED ONLINE; [HTTPS://WWW.CCA.QC.CA/](https://www.cca.qc.ca/))

GANDHI BHAWAN, PANJAB UNIVERSITY BY LE CORBUSIER

- VIEW OF THE ASSEMBLY HALL AND SURROUNDING LANDSCAPE DURING CONSTRUCTION, CHANDIGARH

© FLC/ADAGP, PARIS 2025, P. XX (PHOTOGRAPHER UNKNOWN, ARCHIVES FONDATION LE CORBUSIER, PARIS)

TOM STRALA, ARCHIVE

SCHRÖDER HOUSE (RIETVELD SCHRÖDERHUIS) BY GERRIT THOMAS RIETVELD

- EXTERIOR VIEW, GARDEN FAÇADE

© CENTRAAL MUSEUM UTRECHT / ADAGP, PARIS 2025, P. XX (PHOTO ARCHIVE RIETVELD SCHRÖDERHUIS, UTRECHT)

PORTRAIT OF A YOUNG GERRIT RIETVELD

- STUDIO PHOTOGRAPH, PUBLISHED IN DE STIJL, VOL. 7, NO. 79/84 (1927)

© COLLECTION RIETVELD / ADAGP, PARIS 2025, P. XX (PHOTOGRAPHER UNKNOWN; REPRODUCED VIA WIKIMEDIA COMMONS)

CASCADE RESIDENCE, 1967-1969

- TERRACES AND STRUCTURAL INTERPLAY AT LES ARCS 1600

© CENTRE POMPIDOU / FONDS PERRIAND, PARIS (CHARLOTTE PERRIAND & GUY REY-MILLET; [MEDIATION.CENTREPOMPIDOU.FR](https://www.mediation.centrepompidou.fr))

PORTRAIT OF CHARLOTTE PERRIAND, 1928

- IN HER STUDIO ON PLACE SAINT-SULPICE, PARIS

© ARCHIVES CHARLOTTE PERRIAND / ADAGP, PARIS (REPRODUCED VIA DESIGN MUSEUM EXHIBITION IMAGES: CHARLOTTE PERRIAND: THE MODERN LIFE)

SESC FÁBRICA POMPÉIA, SÃO PAULO

- HISTORICAL VIEW SHOWING INDUSTRIAL STRUCTURES AND EARLY COMPLEX MORPHOLOGY

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PORTRAIT OF LINA BO BARDI

© ARCHIVE, INSTITUTO BARDI / CASA DE VIDRO IN SÃO PAULO, BRAZIL

INTERIOR OF HAUS AM HORN, WEIMAR, 1923

- HISTORICAL VIEW OF THE LIVING ROOM WITH ORIGINAL BAUHAUS FURNISHINGS AND CHAIRS

© BAUHAUS-UNIVERSITÄT WEIMAR, ARCHIV DER MODERNE / BLDAM, BILDARCHIV, NEG.-NR.: 64 H 27 /I24 (REPRODUCED ONLINE; [KLASSIK-STIFTUNG.DE](https://www.klassik-stiftung.de))

PORTRAIT OF MARCEL BREUER

- PUBLICITY PHOTOGRAPH TAKEN FOR THE EXHIBITION THE HOUSE IN THE MUSEUM GARDEN, MUSEUM OF MODERN ART (MOMA)

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